

5G-based Traffic Safety and Management Service for Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility in Cross-Border Scenarios

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Abstract—The EU-funded Horizon 2020 5GMED project aims to promote Cooperative Intelligent Transportation Systems (C-ITS) in Europe by deploying Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) services across international borders. In this context, this paper presents a 5G-based road traffic safety & management service based on the development of multiple actors and components capable of assessing the traffic status and providing the proper information to Connected Vehicles (CVs) through 5G and Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication technologies. Performance evaluation has been carried out through real-world experiments and trials conducted along the 5GMED cross-border corridor (CBC) between Spain and France, leading to interesting findings and lessons learned presented in the conclusion of this paper.

Keywords— *C-ITS, CCAM, V2X, 5G, traffic safety, cross border corridors, DENM, MCM, VAE Server, V2XGW, V2N*

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of the V2X concept combined to the ongoing car softwarization and automation, are drastically reshaping the automotive industry, transforming vehicles into smartphones on wheels and leading to the CCAM concept. As a result, different wireless technologies have been investigated for vehicular communication like Wi-Fi, LTE, 802.11p/ITS-G5, and Cellular-V2X (C-V2X) [1]. However, none of them could meet all the requirements of advanced CCAM services.

The fifth generation of cellular communication (5G) is a promising technology [2], capable of addressing these requirements. In fact, it is not tailored for unique usage and can be adapted to various user profiles in terms of high speed and bandwidth, low latency, high reliability, and scalability. Therefore, it is increasingly investigated by European Research projects within this decade to support the advent of new CCAM services, especially in cross-border scenarios to foster the deployment of C-ITS. For instance, the 5GCroCo project [3] introduced a 5G-based road digitalization system for CCAM in cross-border scenarios. The 5G-CARMEN project [4] focused on streamlining cross-border mobility, by predicting vehicle border crossings and implementing automatic migration of relevant applications and services in the edge, to

ensure seamless connectivity and uninterrupted vehicle operations. In a bid to revolutionize CCAM services, the 5GMob project [5] sheds light on the effectiveness of new mechanisms to reduce service interruptions during handovers and roaming conditions, applied to low-speed automated shuttles.

These past projects highlighted the main challenges and limitations [6], before successfully demonstrating the benefits of 5G and new technologies (e.g., Cloud), in cross-border environments. Moreover, they contributed to the development of new technical solutions that are valuable inputs for standardization bodies (e.g., 3GPP, ETSI, ISO, etc.), to ensure greater industry adoption. Similarly, the 5GMED project [7] [8] also aims to achieve uninterrupted service continuity when vehicles cross international borders but with substantial differences. Indeed, one of the main novelties of 5GMED is the investigation of fully operational 5G standalone (SA) networks, through the deployment of two 5G SA networks covering the Spanish and French segments along the CBC between the cities of Figueras (Spain) and Perpignan (France) to support CCAM and railways services. Moreover, 5GMED is evaluating different roaming optimization techniques over Home-Routed Roaming (HRR) and Local Breakout (LBO) roaming [9].

In this context, the main paper contribution is the design, implementation, and evaluation of a road traffic safety and management service for CCAM in cross-border scenarios, based on 5G and V2X. Involved technologies include ETSI C-ITS standardized Cooperative Awareness Messages (CAMs) and Decentralized Environmental Notification Messages (DENMs) [10], as well as non-standardized Manoeuvre Coordination Messages (MCMs) [11], in addition to the 3GPP/ETSI concept of V2X Application Enabler (VAE) [12]. The latter defines a publish/subscribe exchange mechanism for C-ITS messages based on V2N communications.

In overall, the joint usage of all these technologies and the service evaluation based on 5G SA networks through extensive large-scale trials represent a significant change compared to the state-of-the-art. Finally, the paper aims to demonstrate the

suitability of the 5GMED network architecture for CCAM services, and to provide interesting findings and conclusions able to guide future CCAM services deployments.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the service architecture and main components. Section III details the real experiments carried out on the CBC for service evaluation. Subsequently, trials results are discussed and analyzed in Section IV. Finally, Section V concludes the paper by summarizing the main achievements and findings.

II. 5G-BASED TRAFFIC SAFETY AND MANAGEMENT SERVICE

This service fits within the 5GMED Road Infrastructure Digitalization (RID) Use Case (UC) that aims to elevate road infrastructure to Level A of the Infrastructure Support Levels for Automated Driving (ISAD) [13] classification. This UC investigates several approaches to improve traffic safety and management through rapid data transmission and analysis.

A traditional approach would be to rely on road infrastructure cameras; however, the current proposal follows a more innovative approach, where CVs are equipped with onboard sensors and cameras able to detect road hazards based on Artificial Intelligence (AI). Therefore, the current paper focuses only on this approach, and don't consider a combination of multiple approaches and data sources, although this can be relevant. In addition, the 5GMED project has proposed a network architecture based on several layers to support the operations of challenging CCAM and railways UCs in cross-border scenarios. Therefore, several service components are deployed at the 5GMED Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) & Cloud levels as illustrated in Fig. 1. Doing so enables cross-border cooperation for proper assessment of road hazards along the corridor and their mitigation through immediate dissemination of road hazard notifications (warnings) and traffic strategies to prevent accidents and manage traffic. Such notifications and strategies are delivered to known vehicles through fast, reliable, and low-latency 5G SA networks, following a Vehicle-to-Network (V2N) communication paradigm.

More specifically, information related to the presence of a road hazard detected by a vehicle is shared with the Traffic Management Center (TMC), through a lightweight implementation of a VAE server known as the V2X Gateway (V2XGW). The TMC assesses the situation before notifying close vehicles, currently driving towards the detected road hazard area. This is done by issuing road hazard notifications in the form of DENMs (according to ETSI EN 302 637-3 V1.3.1 [10]); and traffic strategies as MCMs. For recall, the latter message type has not yet been standardized, and its custom implementation combines old concepts from past projects (PAC-V2X, TransAID) [11] and new ones, including traffic guidance regarding closed lanes, speed limit or minimal distance to the preceding vehicle.

The aforementioned approach is in line with the project focus on the collection and dissemination through 5G of floating vehicle data & V2X messages. In the rest of this section, the main service components are presented first, and

Fig. 1: Functional components of the presented service deployed over the 5GMED network architecture

subsequently, datapaths related to road hazard notifications and traffic strategies are discussed.

A. Service components

1) *Traffic Management Center*: It plays a crucial role by monitoring and regulating road traffic to ensure traffic safety and management. To achieve this, it has been designed as a distributed system, where several instances known as TMC Edges are deployed locally and have direct control only on a distinct area of the road to provide reliable low-latency operations. Besides, a single non-latency critical instance is deployed in the Cloud - known as TMC Global - to gather information from TMC Edges and provide a high-level picture of the traffic status. Finally, this distributed system is replicated in both countries in cross-border scenarios.

- **TMC Global**: upon the detection of a road hazard by a vehicle, and relayed by the TMC Edge, the TMC Global evaluates & confirms the hazard situation, and preempts potential traffic problems in upcoming highway sections thanks to its global overview of traffic conditions on all road segments. Therefore, it issues a road hazard notification, and potentially a traffic strategy to ensure efficient traffic safety & management, through HTTP REST API calls. These notifications & strategies are shared with local TMC Edges to allow their proper dissemination to all relevant vehicles. Finally, the TMC Global plays a crucial role in enabling cross-border cooperation, by acting as a single entry point with its peers deployed in other countries, to exchange information about hazardous situations in the nearby sections on both border sides.
- **TMC Edge**: it acts as a localized instance of the TMC global in charge of a specific road section, but still under its supervision. Therefore, some operations of the TMC Global are delegated to it. Moreover, it is designed to collect information from local road-side sensors & cameras (although not considered by this service). Finally, it acts as an interface between the TMC Global and the V2X Gateway in its managed segment, and interactions

with those components are done through HTTP REST API calls.

2) *V2X Gateway*: It is one of the service pillars and has several goals such as ensuring vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) and V2N communications in its service area, by intelligently using available long & short-range communication technologies: 5G, ITS-G5/C-V2X. Furthermore, it acts as an interface between the V2X and non-V2X realms, by exposing HTTP API endpoints for receiving hazard notifications and traffic strategies issued by the TMC, which are later on encoded as DENMs & MCMs able to be understood by CVs. Finally, it implements a simple DENM and MCM subscription mechanism for CVs, where the latter request subscriptions by announcing their presence through CAMs messages.

3) *Connected Vehicles*: Besides being in charge of the initial detection of road hazards, Connected Vehicles can execute traffic strategies issued by the TMC to ensure traffic safety and efficient traffic management. To achieve all of this, they embed the following components:

- **Telematics Control Unit (TCU)**: is in charge of all network communications. It includes a 5G modem to support V2N communication, in addition to a GPS/GNSS positioning device.
- **V2X Protocol Stack**: implements ETSI C-ITS facility messages like CAMs, DENMs & MCMs. In the case of 5GMED, facility messages are sent to the V2XGW on top of UDP & IP for fast, lightweight communication.
- **Smart Sensor**: thanks to AI algorithms, this sensor can detect road hazards that are shared with the TMC through the V2XGW, after being sent by the V2X stack as DENMs [14].

B. Road Hazard Notifications and Traffic Strategies

An important aspect to clarify is related to the generation and delivery of road hazard notifications and traffic strategies in each country. For recall, a hazard detected by a vehicle on the Spanish side is shared with the Spanish TMC. The information is first relayed to the V2XGW as a DENM before being sent to the TMC system through HTTP REST API calls. The distributed TMC system is responsible for checking and validating hazard information. Subsequently, it regenerates a similar road hazard notification that is sent back to CVs (through Spanish V2XGW and TMC Edge). This information is also provided to the French TMC Global to be shared with other vehicles (thanks to the French V2XGW and TMC Edge). Finally, TMC Globals decide independently and in each country whether or not to provide traffic guidance as traffic strategies for better traffic management. This means that DENMs are initially generated by the detecting vehicle and that the same information flows on both sides of the corridor. In contrast, MCMs follow a different data path, since they are issued separately in each country.

Fig. 2: 5GMED Cross-border trials site

III. CROSS BORDER CORRIDOR TRIALS SETUP

A. 5GMED Network Infrastructure

Two 5G SA networks have been deployed on the Spanish and French sides of the Mediterranean CBC between Figueras (Spain) and Perpignan (France) [7], with up to 15 gNBs along the whole corridor. The radio network has been optimized to provide coverage over the highway. The core network was updated by implementing the N14 interface between the French and Spanish Access and Mobility Management Functions (AMF) [15]. This interface is used to share the UE context information between the two AMFs, which results in a substantial decrease in the handover (between two public land mobile networks (PLMN), also known as inter-PLMN handover) interruption time when the UE passes from one country to another. Furthermore, the concept of neutral host [8] was applied in the 5GMED network to further reduce the interruption time. Using this concept, a neutral host will manage the radio sites on the borders, and configure the cells on the two sides of the borders as neighbors and align the time frame configuration of the two networks. This will prevent the UE from scanning the frequency bands to find the new operator when crossing the borders. Finally, to enable the use of MEC, the 5GMED consortium deployed distributed User Plane Functions (dUPF) that allow the deployment of MECs as close as possible to the UEs.

B. Trials Setup

Real experiments of this 5G-based service have been carried out in a specific segment of the 5GMED CBC, spanning on more than 27.5 km (round trip) over the AP7 & A9 highways, respectively from La Jonquera in Spain to Le Boulou in

TCU	A	B
Role	Tx/Rx	Rx
5G SA Modem	Quectel RM510Q-GL	Quectel RM530N-GL
SIM Card	Spanish	French
Serving V2XGW	Spanish	French
Mobility	Mobile	Mobile

TABLE I: Vehicles trial setup

France, as illustrated in Fig. 2. This segment is covered by 5 gNBs part of the 5GMED SA networks (respectively 2 & 3 as part of the Spanish & French 5G SA networks). For these trials, two vehicles/TCUs (in the rest of the paper, the terms vehicle and TCU are used interchangeably) A & B have been equipped with the hardware and software components described in Section II-A3 and illustrated in Fig. 3. Specifically, each vehicle was assigned to a country (Spain for A and France for B), and therefore the vehicles were using SIM cards, and connecting to the V2XGWs belonging to their home country. They were equipped with Quectel RM510Q-GL and RM530N-GL 5G SA modems, configured to use only HRR roaming mode. This setup is summarized in Table I.

To provide a good performance evaluation, several runs have been conducted based on the most significant scenario where both vehicles were moving along the CBC and crossing the border, triggering each time an Inter-PLMN handover. Moreover, vehicle A was configured to periodically (every 2 seconds) transmit road hazards (DENMs), to trigger hazard notifications (DENMs) and traffic strategies (MCMs) sent by the TMC systems and received by both vehicles. Table II provides more details regarding these runs.

Finally, multiple sets of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been defined to evaluate the results of the trials, with a substantial focus on the network behavior and delivery of DENMs & MCMs sent by TMCs. They are defined as follows:

- **Network KPIs:** like the **Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP)** which measures in dBm the level of received signal power in cellular networks; and **Network Interruption** that measures the delay during which a TCU is disconnected from the network.
- **DENM KPIs:** this includes the **DENM End-to-End (E2E) Latency** which is the time difference between the detection of road hazards (by a vehicle smart sensor) and the reception of DENM by a TCU. The service targets an E2E latency below 200ms. Another KPI is the **DENM Reliability** which is the ratio of DENMs successfully delivered by V2XGWs to TCUs. The target value is set to 99.9%.
- **MCM KPIs:** the **MCM E2E Latency** is the time

Runs	Date	Start time	End time	Direction
#1	31/05/2024	13:08	13:18	South
#2	10/06/2024	18:17	18:41	Both
#3	10/06/2024	18:41	19:02	Both
#4	11/06/2024	16:21	16:46	Both
#5	11/06/2024	16:47	17:07	Both

TABLE II: Trials runs details

Fig. 3: Vehicles hardware setup: rooftop antennas (Top), onboard equipment and smart camera (Bottom left), TCU with 5G SA modem (Bottom right)

difference between the issue of a traffic strategy by the TMC Global to MCM reception by a TCU. The service targets a value below 200ms. Finally, **MCM Reliability** is the ratio of MCMs successfully delivered by V2XGWs to TCUs. The target is once again 99.9% of successful delivery.

IV. CROSS BORDER CORRIDOR TRIALS RESULTS

A. Network behavior & results for a single run

A good understanding of the network behavior is fundamental for accurate results analysis & interpretation. Therefore, before presenting the overall results related to DENMs & MCMs delivery, an overview of the network results is provided for a single run (run #3).

To start, Fig. 4 shows the evolution over time of the measured RSRP (top) and cell attachment (bottom) for both TCUs. The most significant network events that occur during the run are reported (between the two plots) and illustrated in each plot as vertical blue (associated with A) and orange (associated with B) lines. These network events include coverage gaps and network changes (New PLMN: France or Spain), illustrated respectively as dotted & dashed-dotted lines.

The results illustrate a typical run along the 5GMED CBC where both vehicles start driving from Spain towards France, They are initially attached to La Jonquera cell before switching to Le Perthus, where a first coverage gap is reported by B, with an RSRP drop up to -120 dbm (18:44). Subsequently, both vehicles reach the border and successfully attach to the French network (event: New PLMN: Fr; cell: Site 09), thanks to an optimized inter-PLMN handover. However, a specific network event reported in the figure as **connectivity loss** occurs. It affects both vehicles that lose data connectivity in the downlink until the connection is reset, although they are still attached to the network with preserved uplink data connectivity.

Fig. 4: Evolution over time of RSRP (top) & Cell attachment (bottom) with main reported network events (middle) for both vehicles during run #3

The vehicles continue their journey towards LeBoulou in France after attaching to both Site 08 & 06. During this process, several coverage gaps are reported, together with important RSRP drops as low as -110 dbm (18:48) and continuous change in cell attachment (Site 08, then 09, and finally 06). After 18:55, vehicles start their journey back to Spain and go through some coverage gaps before successfully attaching to the Spanish network (New PLMN: Sp). Interestingly, no connectivity loss events are reported this time and in this direction.

Overall, network results for the selected run illustrate good RSRP for both TCUs during most of the trip, with averages higher than -90 dbm and peaks up to -50 dbm. However, the presence of coverage gaps and the occurrence of downlink connectivity loss along the CBC, translate into several network interruptions that are summarized in Table III. A unique and short interruption (1 second) is associated with the downlink connectivity loss, whereas those related to coverage gaps last on average 7.8 seconds and for a maximum of 18 seconds. Nevertheless, the 5GMED network infrastructure successfully achieved optimized 5G Inter-PLMN handover, without noticeable network interruptions, as in the case of the network change from France to Spain.

B. DENMs & MCMs results for all runs

As presented earlier, this service aims to deliver road hazard notifications (DENMs) in less than 200 ms. To that end, each TCU computes this E2E latency based on the DENM reception time; and the detection time already encoded in the DENM *detection_time* field.

E2E latency results for both TCUs are illustrated in Fig. 5(a). They reveal an average E2E latency of 100 ms for A, and over the target of 200 ms for B, with many abnormal values over 500 ms for both TCUs. These interesting results, and specifically the substantial difference between A & B E2E latencies, deserve further investigation. Therefore, additional measurement points have been introduced at the V2XGW level, to allow E2E latency decomposition into two distinct components known as the processing & transmission/reception (Tx/Rx) operations latencies. The processing latency reflects the time required to process a road hazard by all of the V2XGW, TMC Edge/Global, whereas the Tx/Rx operations latency is related solely to the amount of time required for exchanging DENMs between V2XGWs and TCUs. These distinct latency measurements are respectively reported in Fig. 5(b) & (c), and results show a higher average processing latency for B compared to A (with an increase of more than 190% from 64 to 187 ms). This is explained by the longer data path for receiving DENMs in case of B, where V2XGWs, TMC Edges and Globals from both countries are involved, as already explained in Section II-B. In the case of A, only the

Network Interruption	Unit	Min	Mean	Max	Std
associated to a coverage gap	ms	995	7897	17979	6868
associated to a connectivity loss	ms	1000	1000	1000	nan

TABLE III: Network interruptions results associated to main network events during run # 3

Fig. 5: DENM E2E Latency (a), Processing Latency (b) and Tx/Rx Latency (c)

Spanish V2XGW, TMC Edge/Global are involved. Moreover, most of the abnormal processing latencies are within 500 ms (outliers). In contrast, the Tx/Rx operation latency for both vehicles is subject to greater variability with very low averages and minimal values (average below 50 ms for A, and between 75 & 100 ms for B). However, many high latencies are observed (even beyond 500ms), which is explained by the coverage gaps that hinder communication. These results show that the processing latency accounts for more than 50% of the overall E2E latency (respectively 54% for A and 64% for B, on average), but when very high latencies are observed they are due to high Tx/Rx latencies (more than 90% of maximum A & B latencies).

Regarding traffic strategies, the data path is different since MCMs are generated separately by each TMC Global, as detailed in Section II-B. Therefore, vehicles compute E2E latency based on the MCM reception time; and the issue time (by the TMC Global) already reported in the MCM *issue_time* field. The results depicted in Fig. 6 show average latencies of around 50 ms and below the target of 200 ms for both vehicles. However, some outliers exist because of the presence of coverage gaps.

Finally, it is important to note that DENMs & MCMs reliability is similar to a packet delivery ratio commonly used in computer networks, but with a substantial difference. In fact, as per standard DENMs are retransmitted several times (during the trials, a single DENM is repeated 10 times every 200ms), therefore, DENM reliability considers only the first DENM occurrence. In contrast, the MCM pre-standard does not include any repetition mechanism; thus, MCMs are sent only once. The related results are summarized in Table IV. They show that the average reliability of DENM and MCM is slightly below 90% (89%), with better results for B (92%) compared to A (85%), something that is explained by the better performance provided by the Quectel RM530N-GL

Fig. 6: MCM E2E Latency

5G SA. Considering the presence of coverage gaps and the usage of a fast but unreliable transport protocol like UDP, these results are good, however they don't meet the target of 99.9%. They also show that DENM retransmission doesn't increase overall reliability when communication is hindered by the presence of coverage gaps. Therefore, addressing such network issues should be done through other mechanisms or by relying on a more reliable transport protocol. The latter aspect represents a new challenge for the large-scale deployment of V2X through V2N communication in general and 5G networks more specifically.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a new 5G-based CCAM Traffic Safety & Management service for C-ITS in cross-border scenarios. The service relies on an innovative approach where road

KPIs	TCUs	Unit	Min	Mean	Max	Std
DENM E2E Latency	A + B	ms	64	209.99	1993	155.50
	A	ms	64	118.36	1903	134.64
	B	ms	203	294.13	1993	122.27
DENM Reliability	A + B	%	0	89.13	100	30.58
	A	%	0	85.73	100	34.75
	B	%	0	92.53	100	25.29
MCM E2E Latency	A + B	ms	26	45.92	914	32.79
	A	ms	46	57.07	204	15.42
	B	ms	26	44.78	914	33.87
MCM Reliability	A + B	%	0	89.27	100	30.96
	A	%	0	85.61	100	35.11
	B	%	0	92.92	100	25.65

TABLE IV: Results summary for DENMs & MCMs E2E latency and reliability

hazards are detected through sensors embedded in vehicles but still supervised by a TMC system in charge of assessing and mitigating these hazards through warning notifications and traffic strategies distributed to connected vehicles. To do so, service components operating at different levels of the 5GMED network architecture cooperate and exchange C-ITS messages like CAMs, DENMs & MCMs, which is facilitated by the implementation of a lightweight V2X VAE Server concept known as V2X Gateway.

Real experiments in the 5GMED CBC show that the designed service is able to deliver useful information related to road safety and traffic management quickly, with E2E latencies below 50 ms for MCM, meeting the target of 200 ms. Achieving the same target regarding DENMs latency has been partial and possible only for vehicle A. In fact, the design choice to enroll all components in both countries (V2XGW, TMC Edge / Global) to deliver DENMs to vehicle B harms overall performance, with an incompressible processing latency accounting for most observations. Therefore, future works should not neglect this aspect, and V2X VAE-like servers operating in cross-border scenarios should interact directly by implementing discovery services supported by TMC systems. Another interesting finding is related to the similar performance observed for DENM and MCM reliability, with good results but still far from the target of 99.9%, despite implementing different solutions to ensure message delivery (unlike MCMs, DENMs are retransmitted several times). These results are due to the presence of coverage gaps along the corridor, but more interestingly pose the question of the right choice of long-range profile for C-ITS messages, including the right choice for the transport protocol to be used (between a lightweight connection less protocol like UDP and a more robust but slower connection-oriented protocol like TCP), in addition to C-ITS service adaptation to V2N communications (e.g. discarding DENM retransmission over V2N). These aspects represent new challenges for the future large-scale deployment of V2X over 5G networks.

Finally, this paper has demonstrated the suitability of the 5GMED network architecture to support the operation of the proposed CCAM Traffic Safety & Management service, by achieving seamless HRR roaming and low latency thanks to 5G SA networks featuring innovative solutions.

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